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ON

Gender Studies: Literature, Culture, Media and Society

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on

“Gender Studies: Literature, Culture, Media and Society”

at

**Yeshwantrao Chavan College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Sillod,
Maharashtra, India**

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**GENDER AND RELIGIOUS IDEOLOGY IN DR. S.L.BHYRAPPA'S
NOVEL 'AVARANA: THE VEIL'****RUGE KAMALAKAR SHIVALINGAPPA**A. R. Burla Mahila Mahavidyalaya,
B. Solapur.**ABSTRACT:**

The present paper is going to unveil the aspects of religious ideology and its impact on women in Dr. S.L.Bhyrappa's novel "Avarana: The Veil". "An ideology is a worldview: a conception of the nature of the universe intended to help structure human behaviour. A religion is an ideology which one's relationship to the universe is personal and relational rather than material and mechanical. A religion is an organic ideology, as opposed to mechanistic ideology. 'Avarana' is a story of Laxmi, a rebellious girl, a filmmaker who gets married to Amir, a Muslim guy and changed her name to Razia. Being young and highly educated Laxmi (Razia) denies all the aspects of religion, rules and regulations of her own caste i.e. Hindu and chooses her own way of life by marrying Amir. At the beginning of the novel both Amir and Razia are of 54. They were 26 when they got married. Born and brought up in the Gandhianwadi family of Narasimhegauda (father of Laxmi) and suddenly getting into Muslim family, Razia urf Laxmi faces numerous problems with her past and present religions Hindu and Islam.

Keywords: *Religious ideology, Hindu, Islam, rebellious, Gandhianwadi, etc.*

ABOUT THE AUTHOR:

Dr. S.L. Bhyrappa has earned his name and fame as a writer and good critic in *Kannada Literature*. His writings are translated into all regional language of India including English. To add to this his every creative writing has gone through more than 10 reprints. This is an evidence of his uniqueness in theme, structure, and characterization in his writing. Starting with "*Bheemkaya*", first published in 1958, Dr. Bhyrappa has authored 24 novels in a career spanning more than five decades. His novel "*Vamshavruksha*" has received the '*Kannada Sahitya Academy Award*' in 1966 and "*Daatu (Crossing Over)*" received both '*Kannada and the Kendra Sahitya Academy Award*' in 1975. Apart from this he is honoured with following awards.

1. Bendre National Award (2020)

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2. Padma Shri Award (2016)

3. Saraswati Samman Award (2011)

The novel by *Dr. Bhyrappa 'Avarana: The Veil'* is thought provoking and controversial. At the very beginning of the novel Bhyrappa expresses the meaning of the title 'Avarana' in following words - "*The act of concealing truth is known as 'avarana', and that of projecting untruth is called 'vikshepa'. When these occur at the level of an individual, it is known as 'avidya' and when they occur at the level of a group or the world, it is known as 'maya'.*"

The book opens with Raziya (Laxmi), a middle aged documentary filmmaker, a feminist by heart and soul, is married to Amir. She always keeps talking about gender equality. The plot opens when Raziya was assigned to do documentary movies on the ruins of Hampi, the cultural capital of Karnataka. Her husband, Amir is the director in charge of the documentary movie. The main motive of the documentary movie, to portray Hampi as a resemblance of a Hindu-Muslim brotherhood. When Razia learns to understand the actual causes of the destruction in Hampi, she began to go through her own life memories of her past (before marriage).

After getting married with Amir, Raziya (Laxmi) tries to keep her rebellious attitude but her family and community forces her to practice ideologies of Islam like offering Namaz five times in a day, wearing *Burkha (veil)* etc. At some stage Amir tries to threaten her that he will give divorce by using *Triple Talaq* system. Her mother-in-law becomes all the more strict by imposing upon her the tenets of her religion to make her devout and true Muslim wife and daughter-in-law because they have also the fear of excommunication from the community. She recommends her to offer *Namaz* five times daily at a prescribed place, the compulsory *Namaz* on Fridays and the forced fasting from dawn to dusk in the month of *Ramzan*. Her father-in-law is mild but shrewder in taming the liberty of Laxmi. For them, Razia is the *zeenat (pride)* of their home and she must not venture out of her home. Razia feels that this kind of attitude evinced by Amir and his parents veers close to arbitrariness where the idea of individuality does not exist. This falsity in religious way of life costs them dear both personally and professionally.

At every stage she tries hard to go against all these restrictions but her love towards her husband and her duty towards her in law's house compels her to accept everything though it is against her will.

It is said that when it comes to preserving our own identity, we try to find out our roots. Likewise, after listening the news of her father's death, Razia decides to go back to her village to see her house in Hasana district. The village which she left before 28 years, protesting her family to get marry Amir. As she entered in her house, she examined a small library, built by her father. There she found several volumes of books, about Islam's encounter with Hindus. After reading those books and some notes by her father, her past begins to play in her mind. She was feminist activist and successful bright student in her college. With her modern mindset, she decided to marry her classmate Amir. Despite getting married to Amir, Razia urf Lakshmi never understood, why she has to change her religion and practice Islam. In reality,

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Amir was not as broad minded as Raziya thought he was. He insisted her to change her religion, otherwise, their marriage will not be accepted by his parents. Her first rift with Amir comes up when he forces her to eat beef. Amir and Raziya had a son named Nazir, who graduated from a USA university but found a job in Southy Arabia.

On the other hand we have the character of Prof. Shastri, who represents himself as a progressive thinker and he is good orator. He got married with a Christian girl. Like Raziya urf Laxmi (after marriage), Prof. Shastri's daughter finds herself in a dilemma whether to follow her mother's Christian religion or her father's Hindu religion in her school days. He gives suggestion to Laxmi that "*An inter-religious marriage is far more revolutionary than an inter-caste marriage!*" The novel focuses on the History of India as well as how the region and it's rules are used to dominate women. The society forces women to accept the religion and it's ideologies irrespective of her choice and freedom. We can say that religion and it's ideologies are used as a mean to dominate and substitute women in the society. Overall, the book raises important question of Hinduism on a comparison with Christianity and Islam. The Western countries have already rejected the notion of keeping religion as a base to rule the country and brought in democracy. So the India is known as biggest democratic nation.

At the end it is found that each character belonging to different religion in the novel, thinks that his/her own religion is superior than the other and tries to impose it on the other. In between women become the victims of so called *religious ideologies*. We must learn that the religion is a social- cultural system of designated behaviour and practices, morals etc. and ideology is a universal conception to help the structure of human behaviour. So we must not use the religious ideologies to dominate or marginalize any other part of the society.

REFERENCES:

1. Bhyrappa, S.L. Avarana: The Veil. Trans. Sandeep Baalakrahna. New Delhi. Rupa Publication, 2014.
2. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aavarana>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/S._L._Bhyrappa